

Optimal Area Polygonisation Problems: Mixed Integer Linear Programming Models

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Abstract

This paper describes approaches to finding polygons with maximum and minimum area through a given set of points on the Euclidean plane. Both problems are \mathcal{NP} -hard and of interest in Computational Geometry. They have been extensively studied, although only the recent literature presents mathematical formulations to consistently find optimal solutions to instances from a benchmark collection with up to 25 points. We present and compare eight new Mixed Integer Linear Programming models for the two problems. Four represent a polygon as a solution to the Asymmetric Travelling Salesman Problem, while the other four use the Symmetric Travelling Salesman Problem representation. Six of the models select triangles to compute the area of a polygon, while the other two models select subpolygons. A computational analysis on the benchmark collection shows that one of our new formulations can consistently solve most of the benchmark instances with up to 50 points. The success of our proposal is a linear system to select a triangulation of the point set, a partition of the triangulation to cover the internal and external area of a polygon, and a representation of the polygon as the solution of an Asymmetric Travelling Salesman Problem.

Keywords: Computational Geometry, Triangulations, Polygonisations, Mixed Integer Linear Programming, Travelling Salesman Problem.

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1. Introduction

Given a finite set of points and a cost matrix representing the travel cost between each pair of points, the well-known *Travelling Salesman Problem* (TSP) looks for a sequence of the points such that a closed route (tour) following that sequence has the minimum cost. When the cost matrix is a *metric* between the points, the problem is called *Metric TSP*. A particular case of the Metric TSP occurs when the metric is the Euclidean norm, happening when the points are in the Cartesian plane, each one i is associated with coordinates (α_i, β_i) , and the travel cost between point i and point j is $\sqrt{(\alpha_i - \alpha_j)^2 + (\beta_i - \beta_j)^2}$. The problem is then called *Euclidean TSP* and aims at computing a polygon whose vertices are the given points and with the shortest perimeter. The computational complexity of the Euclidean TSP is interesting since it is an \mathcal{NP} -hard problem (see Papadimitriou (1977)), but it is not in \mathcal{NP} because the square root of a number may be irrational and, therefore, there is no efficient procedure to compute the total travel cost of a tour. Another interesting property of the Euclidean TSP is that optimal solutions are simple polygons, meaning their line segments may intersect only at the given points. This property has been used in the literature to describe Polynomial-Time Approximation Schemes (i.e. algorithms that compute, in time polynomial in the size of the problem instance, a solution within a factor of $(1 + \epsilon)$ of the optimal solution for any fixed $\epsilon > 0$). The property does not hold when the objective function sense is reversed and the aim is to compute a polygon with the longest perimeter (known as *Maximum TSP*).

Our manuscript concerns two problems closely related to the Euclidean TSP and the Maximum TSP. They consist of finding sequences of the given points such that the internal area is minimal in one problem and maximal in the other problem. The point sequence of points, seen above as a tour, is now seen as a polygon. The optimisation problems are named MINAREA and MAXAREA, respectively, and both together *Optimal Area polygonisation Problem* (OAP), of interest in Computational Geometry (see e.g. Mark Berg and Schwarzkopf (1997)). Computational Geometry delves into various challenges surrounding the construction of geometric objects from a finite set of points on a plane. Tasks like triangulations of point sets, Voronoi diagrams, arrangements, etc., can be considered within this field of research. As our paper remarks, particularly close to the OAP are the *Triangulation Problems*, where one must look for triangles with vertices spanning a given point set (see e.g. Dantzig et al. (1985), Loera et al. (2010)). Some problems are optimisation problems, like the *Minimum Weight Triangula-*

tion Problem (see e.g. Kyoda et al. (1997)), where the weight of a triangle is the perimeter of the triangle, and the aim is to find a triangulation with minimal total weight. Other problems are feasibility questions, like checking whether there exists a triangulation using only line segments in a given set. The mentioned optimisation problem is \mathcal{NP} -hard (see Mulzer and Rote (2008)), and the mentioned feasibility problem is \mathcal{NP} -complete (see Lloyd (1977)).

Fekete (2000) shows that MINAREA and MAXAREA (and generalisations in higher-dimensional spaces) are \mathcal{NP} -complete. Both problems garnered significant attention during a global competition called “Computational Geometry: Solving Hard Optimisation Problems” (CGSHOP 2019)¹. Held in 2019, the contest tasked participants with developing effective algorithms to solve (exactly and/or heuristically) a diverse range of benchmark instances. Seven papers were published in a special issue of the *ACM Journal of Experimental Algorithmics* devoted to this challenge. Demaine et al. (2022) surveyed publications related to the MINAREA and MAXAREA problems until 2019. Five papers were devoted to heuristic algorithms, and two papers were devoted to exact algorithms. Heuristic procedures are described by Crombez et al. (2022), Goren et al. (2022), Eder et al. (2022), and Ramos et al. (2022a). Fekete et al. (2022) and Ramos et al. (2022b) solve exactly the MINAREA and MAXAREA problems. Fekete et al. (2022) present exact algorithms based on two Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) models. The first formulation models the polygon as a counterclockwise-oriented circuit visiting all the given points, and it needs an additional point (reference point) to define the cost of an arc equal to the area between this arc and the reference point, with the sign depending on whether the arc is clockwise oriented or anticlockwise oriented. The second formulation aims at selecting triangles to cover the interior of the optimal polygon, and the major drawback is the connectivity constraints between the selected triangles. Ramos et al. (2022b) present an alternative approach to force the connectivity constraints, consisting of finding a tree spanning all the selected triangles in a graph. While computationally, the triangle-based model showed better results than the other formulations, it is based on $O(n^6)$ variables. The formulation is the best approach in the literature. On a benchmark collection of instances for the CGSHOP 2019 challenge, this formulation allowed finding all optimal solutions for instances with 10 and 15 points, some with 20, a few with 25, and none with 30.

¹<https://cgshop.ibr.cs.tu-bs.de/competition/cg-shop-2019/>

Our paper describes eight new MILP models to solve the MINAREA and MAXAREA problems. Four represent the polygon as an oriented tour, and the other four as a non-oriented tour. Six models compute the objective function based on selecting triangles, either inside the polygon, outside the polygon, or both. The other two models replace triangles with subpolygons. After having implemented all variants, there is one that succeeded in finding optimal solutions to *all* the benchmark instances with up to 30 points. Even more, we apply this new model to larger benchmark instances, and it finds the optimal solutions to *all* instances with up to 45 points, and most of the instances with 50 points. Our major contribution is a set of linear systems to model the selection of triangles and subpolygons. The polygon is modelled with TSP constraints, and the non-crossing edges requirement is implicit in the linear systems.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 gives some definitions and notations of MINAREA and MAXAREA. Section 3 describes two MILP models taken from the literature. Section 4 introduces our new MILP formulations. Section 5 describes valid inequalities and other implementation details. Section 6 analyses computational experiments on benchmark instances. The paper ends with conclusions.

2. Definitions and notations

This section introduces the notation needed in the rest of the paper. We assume to be working on the Cartesian plane \mathbb{R}^2 with the Euclidean norm, and we are given the Cartesian coordinates of the points in N . Without loss of generality, and in coherence with benchmark instances in the literature, the coordinates are assumed to be integer numbers. The set of all convex combinations of points in N , known as the *convex hull* of N , is denoted by $\mathcal{CH}(N)$. Let N' be the subset of N on the boundary of $\mathcal{CH}(N)$. Given two points i and j on the plane, $\mathcal{CH}(\{i, j\})$ is the line segment between these points and, for simplicity, we denote it by $[i, j]$ or $[j, i]$ indistinctly. A *polygon* P is a region of the plane bounded by a finite collection of line segments forming a simple closed curve which is the homeomorphic image of a disk, i.e. it is a certain deformation of a disk. Each line segment on the polygon's border is called an *edge*, and the extreme point of an edge is called a *vertex*. Given N , a *polygonisation of N* is a polygon P whose vertex set is N . A polygon is *simple* if its edges' intersections occur only at its vertices. Thus, an edge of a simple polygon cannot include a third point of N . For the rest of this manuscript, we refer to simple polygons only.

(a) MINAREA. Area = 9096,
Perimeter = 854.50355

(b) MAXAREA. Area = 17532,
Perimeter = 659.91797

(c) EUCLIDEAN TSP. Area = 16096,
Perimeter = 589.25625

(d) MAXIMUM TSP. Area = 11974,
Perimeter = 928.97496

Figure 1: Optimal solutions for the instance `uniform-0000010-1`.

The Jordan Curve Theorem states that a polygon P divides $\mathcal{CH}(N)$ into two disjoint regions: the *interior* and the *exterior*. A line segment connecting two vertices of P and not crossing an edge of P is called an *internal diagonal* when the whole segment lies in the interior of P and an *external diagonal* when it lies in the exterior. In this paper, the area of the polygon P means the area $c(P)$ of its interior region. We assume $N \neq N'$, thus $|N| > |N'| \geq 3$, any polygonisation P of N is non-convex, and $c(\mathcal{CH}(N)) > c(P) > 0$. MINAREA and MAXAREA look for a polygonisation P of N with minimum and maximum area $c(P)$, respectively. Figure 1 shows optimal solutions for the MINAREA and MAXAREA problems with ten points from Ramos et al. (2022b). Optimal solutions for the Euclidean TSP and the Maximum TSP with non-crossing edges are also displayed. The four pictures confirm that, while the problems are related, they may all have different optimal objective values (and therefore different optimal solutions).

Triangles are useful objects for computing the area of a polygon. Let V be the set of *all* triangles whose three vertices are in N , discarding triangles containing a fourth point in N and triangles with the three vertices in a line. We assume that each triangle is counterclockwise oriented, meaning that a triangle with vertices $\{i, j, k\} \subset N$ can be uniquely represented by three (oriented) *arcs* $\{(i, j), (j, k), (k, i)\}$. Let V_{ij} be the subset of triangles in V containing the arc (i, j) . Graphically, V_{ij} and V_{ji} represent the triangles on the left and right, respectively, of a line segment $[i, j]$ with $i, j \in N$. Trivially, $|V_{ij} \cup V_{ji}| \leq |N| - 2$.

For some formulations in our paper, a polygon is represented as a Hamiltonian circuit with non-crossing arcs on a directed graph $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$ where N is the node set, and the above-introduced arcs define A . The previous assumption on the triangles' counterclockwise orientation helps us to have a unique representation of a polygon: a *tour* is a counterclockwise Hamiltonian circuit in $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$. Following the points along a tour, the interior region of the polygon is on the left, and the exterior region is on the right. Let A' be the subset of A corresponding to line segments on the boundary of $\mathcal{CH}(N)$; these arcs determine a counterclockwise circuit spanning N' . Let $A'' = A \setminus A'$ represent the set of all possible (internal or external) diagonals. ($|A''| \geq 1$.)

For other formulations in our paper, a polygon is represented as a non-oriented Hamiltonian tour with non-crossing edges in the undirected graph $\mathcal{G}(N, E)$ where N is the node set and $E = \{\{i, j\} : (i, j) \in A\}$. Let $E' = \{\{i, j\} \in E : (i, j) \in A'\}$ be the edges on the boundary of $\mathcal{CH}(N)$, and $E'' = E \setminus E'$ be the set of all possible (internal or external) diagonals. ($|E''| \geq 1$.)

The constraint that the polygon must be simple (called *non-crossing edges requirement*) implies an incompatibility between some pairs of line segments. Precisely, a pair of line segments $[i, j]$ and $[k, l]$ are *incompatible* when there exists a common point to both, not in $\{i, j, k, l\}$. We denote by I_2 the set of all pairs of incompatible line segments with vertices in N . Observe that no pair in I_2 includes a line segment on the border of $\mathcal{CH}(N)$, meaning that $\{(i, j), (j, i), (k, l), (l, k)\} \subset A''$ when $\{[i, j], [k, l]\} \in I_2$.

Two triangles s and t are *incompatible* when the interior regions of s and t are not disjoint, and they are *adjacent* when there is an edge $\{i, j\} \in E''$ such that $s \in V_{ij}$ and $t \in V_{ji}$. We denote by I_3 the set of all pairs $\{s, t\}$ being s and t incompatible triangles in V , and F the set of all pairs $\{s, t\}$ being s and t adjacent triangles in V . We denote by $\mathcal{G}(V, F)$ the undirected graph that has a node for each triangle $t \in V$ and an edge $e = \{s, t\} \in F$ for each pair of adjacent triangles s and t . Observe that $\mathcal{G}(V, F)$ is a connected

graph where a node's degree is at most three.

This paper uses the following standard graph notation. For $S \subset N$, let $A(S) = \{(i, j) \in A : i, j \in S\}$, $\delta^+(S) = \{(i, j) \in A : i \in S, j \in N \setminus S\}$ and $\delta^-(S) = \{(i, j) \in A : i \in N \setminus S, j \in S\}$. For $S \subset N$, let $E(S) = \{(i, j) \in E : i, j \in S\}$ and $\delta(S) = \{(i, j) \in E : i \in S, j \in N \setminus S \text{ or } i \in N \setminus S, j \in S\}$.

A triangulation T of a polygon P is a pair-disjoint subset of triangles such that the union is the interior area of P . In this paper, we call this triangulation *internal* because we also consider another triangulation T' covering the external area of the polygon within the convex hull, which we call the *external* triangulation of P . A triangulation of the set of points N is defined in the literature as a pair-disjoint subset of triangles such that the union is $\mathcal{CH}(N)$. Thus, the union of the internal and external triangulations of a polygon P is a triangulation of its set of vertices N . Any internal triangulation T of P includes $|N|-2$ triangles and $|N|-3$ non-crossing internal diagonals. Any external triangulation T' of P includes $|N|-|N'|$ triangles and $|N|-|N'|$ non-crossing external diagonals. Thus, a triangulation of N contains $2|N|-|N'|-2$ triangles and involves $3|N|-|N'|-3$ non-crossing line segments. It is also folklore (see e.g. Loera et al. (2010)) that the *dual graph* of a triangulation T of P , which is the subgraph of $\mathcal{G}(V, F)$ induced by T , is a tree (with each node of degree at most three). This tree can be extended to have the following result:

Lemma 1. *A polygon triangulation corresponds to a binary tree where each internal node (with degree three) corresponds to a triangle and each leaf node (with degree one) corresponds to an edge of the polygon.*

The above result refers to internal triangulations, but it also applies to external triangulations, replacing the word “tree” with “forest”. Figure 2 shows two examples, with T in grey colour, T' in white colour, and the binary trees from T in red colour.

Triangulations are of interest when solving OAP for two reasons. One reason is that the area of a polygon reduces to the summation of the triangles' areas. Given a triangle $t \in V$, let c_t be the area of t . Then, the area of a polygon P can be computed as $c(P) = \sum_{t \in T} c_t$ for any internal triangulation T of P . Alternatively, if T' is an external triangulation of P , then $c(P) = c(\mathcal{CH}(N)) - \sum_{t \in T'} c_t$. Another reason, and more important, is that triangulations suggest a nice alternative to model the non-crossing edges requirement, as Section 4 shows. Before, Section 3 summarises how this requirement is formulated in previous articles.

Figure 2: Examples of triangulations of the polygons in Figures 1a and 1b.

3. Known models

This section presents mathematical formulations taken from the recent literature on the MINAREA and the MAXAREA. One formulation is based on the directed graph $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$, determining the optimal polygon by selecting arcs in the graph to have a Hamiltonian circuit. Other formulations are based on the larger undirected graph $\mathcal{G}(V, E)$, modelling the optimal polygon as a selection of triangles. For this reason, the first one is called the *arc-based* formulation, and the others are called the *triangle-based* formulations.

3.1. Arc-Based Formulation

The first mathematical formulations for the MINAREA and the MAXAREA were introduced by Fekete et al. (2022) with the name “Edge-Based Formulation”. It is renamed here as “Arc-Based Formulation” because it makes use of binary variables related to the *arcs* of a directed graph, and we introduce a different formulation in Section 4.5 using binary variables related to *edges* of an undirected graph. We now present the formulations in Fekete et al. (2022).

Consider a given finite set N of points and one additional (arbitrary but fixed) reference point $r \notin N$. For any pair i, j in N , let c_{ij} be the area of the triangle if $\{(i, j), (j, r), (r, i)\}$ is counterclockwise oriented, and minus this number otherwise. It is known in the literature as the *signed area*. Then, the area of any (simple) polygonisation of N can be computed by considering the polygon as a circuit and adding c_{ij} for each arc (i, j) along this circuit. The result is a positive or negative number depending on whether the circuit orientation is counterclockwise or clockwise, respectively. Hence, MAXAREA

can be mathematically formulated as the Asymmetric TSP with no crossing arcs. More precisely, for each $a \in A$, let x_a be a binary variable to determine whether a is in the circuit representing the polygonisation. A formulation for MAXAREA is:

$$\min/\max \sum_{a \in A} c_a x_a \quad (1)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{a \in \delta^+(i)} x_a = \sum_{a \in \delta^-(i)} x_a = 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in N \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{a \in A(S)} x_a \leq |S| - 1 \quad \text{for all } S \subset N \quad (3)$$

$$x_a \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } a \in A \quad (4)$$

$$x_{ij} + x_{ji} + x_{kl} + x_{lk} \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } \{[i, j], [k, l]\} \in I_2. \quad (5)$$

Constraints (2)–(4) force a Hamiltonian circuit on the directed graph $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$ and Inequalities (5) guarantee the non-crossing edge requirement.

Both maximising and minimising in (1) end with polygons with maximum area, and the difference is the circuit's orientation. By our definition of A in Section 2, where the reverse arcs in A' are excluded from A , the two optimisation problems may find different optimal polygons. But still, the above model cannot solve the MINAREA without additional constraints to forbid clockwise-oriented circuits. To this end, Fekete et al. (2022) introduce inequalities called *Slab Constraints*. These inequalities use a straight line with points of N on both sides and no point of N on the line. This line intersects some arcs in any Hamiltonian circuit, and these arcs alternate in direction when crossing the line. The inequalities force the first selected arc to be counterclockwise, the second to be clockwise, etc. To be more precise, let us consider a vertical straight line. Going from bottom to top along this line, the first intersected edge must correspond to an arc in the circuit oriented from left to right, the next from right to left, and so on until we reach the last one, which must be oriented from right to left. To formally write the inequalities, let $(i_1, j_1), \dots, (i_k, j_k)$ be the arcs in A intersecting the vertical line from left to right. Then the slab inequalities for the fixed straight line are:

$$0 \leq \sum_{l=1}^m (x_{i_l j_l} - x_{j_l i_l}) \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } m = 1, \dots, k. \quad (6)$$

They force the first arc (i, j) in the circuit crossing the line to have i on the left and j on the right, hence the circuit is counterclockwise oriented. While the slab constraints related to one straight line are enough to have a valid formulation, Fekete et al. (2022) include the slab constraints related to (at most) $n - 1$ parallel straight lines with (at least) a vertex of N between two adjacent lines. Not surprisingly, Model (1)–(6) solves larger instances when dealing with MAXAREA, where slab constraints are unnecessary.

3.2. Triangle-based Formulation

We now present another model, first introduced by Fekete et al. (2022) and later extended by Ramos et al. (2022b). It aims at selecting a subset of triangles $T \subset V$ to cover the internal area of a polygonisation of N . Let y_t be a binary variable for each $t \in V$, equal to one when the triangle t is selected for the optimal T . Then a formulation for MINAREA and MAXAREA is:

$$\min/\max \sum_{t \in V} c_t y_t \quad (7)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{t \in V_i} y_t \geq 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in N \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{t \in U} (1 - y_t) + \sum_{t \in \eta(U)} y_t \geq 1 \quad \text{for all } U \subset V : 0 < |U| < |N| - 2 \quad (9)$$

$$y_t \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } t \in V \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{t \in V} y_t = |N| - 2 \quad (11)$$

$$y_s + y_t \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } \{s, t\} \in I_3 \quad (12)$$

where V_i represents triangles with a vertex in i , and $\eta(U) = \{s \in V \setminus U : \{s, t\} \in F, t \in U\}$ represents triangles outside U adjacent to the triangles inside U . Inequalities (8) guarantee a selected triangle reaching each vertex. Inequalities (9) ensure the connectivity between the selected triangles: any too-small subset of selected triangles must be adjacent to another selected triangle. Constraints (10) force the variables to be binary. Equation (11) requires selecting the correct number of triangles to cover the internal area of the polygon, and it plays a fundamental role in this formulation because, without this equation, the selected triangles could cover either the interior of the polygon or the exterior of the polygon. In other words, no matter whether the objective function minimises or maximises, the above model

without Equation (11) solves either MINAREA or MAXAREA, but it is unknown a priori. Fortunately, a triangulation of the exterior of a polygon requires fewer than $|N|-2$ triangles; thus, Equation (11) and the connectivity inequalities (9) guarantee to select only triangles in the interior of the polygon. Inequalities (12) are the non-crossing edges requirement.

Experimental results in Fekete et al. (2022) reveal the disadvantages of the Model (7)–(12) when compared to Model (1)–(6). The authors remark that the formulation and the branch-and-bound search require a lot of space on the computer due to the large number of Inequalities (12). We also emphasise that Inequalities (9) require a sophisticated separation approach to be embedded in a proper branch-and-cut algorithm, i.e. when violated inequalities are desired to be generated, not only on integer solutions but also on fractional solutions. For a given (integer or fractional) solution y^* , it is easy (polynomial-time solvable) to find a non-empty subset U minimising $\sum_{t \in U} (1 - y_t^*) + \sum_{s \in \eta(U)} y_s^*$ with a min-cut algorithm on a suitably defined incapacitated network, but it is not so easy when one also needs U with at most $|N|-3$ triangles. Indeed, the separation problem of Inequalities (9) is a cardinality-constrained min-cut problem proved to be strongly \mathcal{NP} -hard in Bruglieri et al. (2004).

Ramos et al. (2022b) formulate the connectivity requirements differently: there must be a *tree* in the subgraph of $\mathcal{G}(V, F)$ spanning the triangles in $T = \{t \in V : y_t = 1\}$, the internal triangulation of the polygon. The literature on tree-related optimisation problems is extensive, including some polyhedral descriptions. To this end, a second family of binary variables (now associated with the large set F) is introduced: for each pair of adjacent triangles $f = \{s, t\} \in F$, the binary variable w_f assumes value 1 if s and t are both selected triangles, and 0 otherwise. Then, the extended model, called **Tree-Model** in Ramos et al. (2022b), is the triangle-based formulation (7)–(12) with Inequalities (9) replaced by

$$\sum_{f \in F} w_f = |N| - 3 \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{f \in \delta(U)} w_f \geq y_s + y_t - 1 \quad \text{for all } U \subset V, t \in U, s \in V \setminus U \quad (14)$$

$$w_f \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } f \in F. \quad (15)$$

Equations (13) force the tree to span all the triangles in T . Inequalities (14) guarantee a path between any pair of triangles in T , i.e. the connectivity of the tree structure. Constraints (15) force the variables to be binary, and it is fundamental because the tree spans only a subset T of W .

The LP relaxation of the **Tree-Model** is strengthened in Ramos et al. (2022b) with the following inequalities:

$$y_t \leq \sum_{f \in \delta(t)} w_f \leq \alpha_t y_t \quad \text{for all } t \in V \quad (16)$$

where α_t is an upper bound on the number of adjacent triangles to t . This upper bound is 3 for all triangles, but it reduces to 2 when t includes one arc in A' , and to 1 when t includes two arcs of A' . The left-side inequality in (16) is already in (14) when $|U|=1$.

Ramos et al. (2022b) empirically compare seven variants of this extended model. The best variant (named “Tree-model-7” in the article) is the above model with two other families of linear constraints. The first family is named “edge biclique inequalities” and states that, for each pair of vertices $i, j \in N$, with the line segment $[i, j]$ not on the convex hull boundary, at most one triangle in V_{ij} can be selected, i.e.:

$$\sum_{t, s \in V_{ij} \cup V_{ji}} w_{\{s, t\}} \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E''.$$

The second family is named “convex hull chords equations” and states that an optimal tour representing a (simple) polygon cannot cross the convex hull $\mathcal{CH}(N)$; thus, the number of triangles in T , adjacent to a line segment $[i, j]$ with $i, j \in N'$, is either zero or two. To model this observation, the authors introduce a binary variable z_e for each pair $e \in E_I''$ and extend the model with:

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij} \cup V_{ji}} y_t = 2z_e \quad \text{for all } e = \{i, j\} \in E_I'' \quad (17)$$

$$z_e \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } e \in E_I''. \quad (18)$$

According to Ramos et al. (2022b), Equations (17) in the **Tree-Model** generate similar computational results to the disaggregated equations:

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t = \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y_t = z_e \quad \text{for all } e = \{i, j\} \in E_I''.$$

Ramos et al. (2022b) also conclude that Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18) outperforms Model (1)–(6), especially when solving MINAREA instances (where the slab constraints (6) play a fundamental role).

The LP relaxation of Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18) could provide stronger LP bounds if the connectivity inequalities (14) were replaced by

$$\sum_{f \in F(U)} w_f \leq \sum_{s \in U \setminus \{t\}} y_s \quad \text{for all } U \subset V \text{ and } t \in U,$$

whose separation problem is still polynomial-time solvable. However, the space inconvenience due to (12) and reported in Fekete et al. (2022) is still in Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18) which, in addition, faces the inconvenience of dealing with the $O(n^6)$ binary variables w_f . For that reason, our research does not go further in this direction. Instead, we propose in the next section alternative triangle-based models where the connectivity requirement is formulated through a TSP structure on the graph $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$, as in Model (1)–(6), rather than through a tree structure on the large graph $\mathcal{G}(V, F)$, as in Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18).

4. New models

We now present three families of MILP formulations for MINAREA and MAXAREA inspired by the formulations in the previous section. The first family consists of four models using the triangle-based variables in Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18) and the Asymmetric TSP representation of a polygon in Model (1)–(6). A second family replaces triangles with subpolygons for the variables and the constraints, still using the Asymmetric TSP representation. The third family exploits working on the Euclidean plane and replaces the Asymmetric TSP representation by a Symmetric one.

4.1. Selecting internal triangles

This section describes a model based on the binary variables x_a of Model (1)–(6) and the variables y_t of Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18). Indistinctly, we write x_a or x_{ij} when $a = (i, j)$. Variables x_a represent a polygon as an oriented circuit following the vertices in counterclockwise order. This means that, for each arc (i, j) in the circuit (i.e. $x_{ij} = 1$), any internal triangulation T of a polygon includes one triangle on the left (i.e. a triangle in V_{ij}) and no triangle on the right (i.e. a triangle in V_{ji}). Otherwise, when an arc a is not in the circuit (i.e. $x_a = 0$), the number of triangles in T on both sides of a must coincide. Precisely, the mathematical model is the objective function (1) subject to the Asymmetric TSP constraints with the no-crossing edges

requirement, for example (2)–(5), and

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t = x_{ij} \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A' \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t - \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y_t = x_{ij} - x_{ji} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \quad (20)$$

$$x_{ij} \leq \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t \leq 1 - x_{ji} \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A'' \quad (21)$$

$$y_t \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in V. \quad (22)$$

For each arc $(i, j) \in A'$, Equation (19) selects one triangle in V_{ij} only when (i, j) is in the circuit, meaning that such a triangle is external; recall that (j, i) is not in A and $V_{ji} = \emptyset$ when $(i, j) \in A'$. Equations (20) force that the number of selected triangles in V_{ij} and V_{ji} must coincide when (i, j) and (j, i) are not in the circuit. Constraints (21) select one triangle from V_{ij} (i.e. on the arc left) and no one from V_{ji} (i.e. on the arc right) when (i, j) is in the Hamiltonian circuit.

Theorem 2. *When the variables x_{ij} represent a Hamiltonian circuit with non-crossing edges, all the extreme solutions of (19)–(22) are integers.*

Proof. Consider a non-integer solution y^* and let ϵ be a tiny positive value. When there is a triangle $t \in V_{ij}$ with $0 < y_t^* < 1$, then there is another triangle $s \in V_{ij}$ such that $y_s^* + y_t^* \leq 1$. Hence, if we replace y_t^* by $y_t^* + \epsilon$, we can also replace y_s^* by $y_s^* - \epsilon$ to not altering the sum on the diagonal (i, j) . We now show how to construct two solutions so that y^* is a convex combination of both. Since y^* has fractional values, select t with $0 < y_t^* < 1$. One solution is created by recursively adding ϵ to all adjacent triangles, starting from t , and the other solution is created by recursively subtracting ϵ . The recursive propagation is possible because of Lemma 1. \square

The above result is consistent with Klincsek (1980), who gave a polynomial-time algorithm for finding a polygon triangulation of minimal weight. Equations (22) are also observed in Yousefi and Young (2014) for finding a point-set triangulation of minimal weight, which is an \mathcal{NP} -hard problem.

Model (1)–(5) and (19)–(22) is referred to by MT1D since it uses triangles, a directed tour, and it optimises the internal area of the polygon. It is worth observing that MT1D does not need the slab inequalities (6) which is the major drawback of Model (1)–(6) when solving MINAREA instances. Also, MT1D does not need the large family of inequalities (12), which is the major drawback of Model (7)–(8) and (10)–(18).

4.2. Selecting external triangles

This section presents an alternative formulation by observing that the optimal polygon is always inside the convex hull of N . The area of the convex hull of N is a constant, denoted by $c(\mathcal{CH}(N))$, and it is computable in polynomial time. Thus, the optimisation problem can consider either the internal area of the polygon (as done in the previously presented formulations), or the external area (inside the convex hull). Motivated by this alternative procedure to compute the area of a solution, rather than finding an internal triangulation T of the optimal polygon, as done in Model MT1D, this section formulates the problem of finding an external triangulation T' of the polygon. It means selecting one triangle for each vertex in $N \setminus N'$. Intuitively, one must select a triangle on the right of each arc in the circuit, except when the arc is on the convex-hull boundary, i.e. in A' .

While we keep x_a for selecting the edges, as in Models (1)–(6) and MT1D, we use y'_t instead of y_t to emphasise that a triangle t is now selected outside the polygon (say, an external triangle). The new model is (1)–(5) and

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t = 1 - x_{ij} \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A' \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t - \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y'_t = x_{ji} - x_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \quad (24)$$

$$x_{ji} \leq \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t \leq 1 - x_{ij} \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A'' \quad (25)$$

$$y'_t \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in V. \quad (26)$$

Theorem 3. *When the variables x_{ij} represent a Hamiltonian circuit with non-crossing edges, all the extreme solutions of (23)–(26) are integers.*

For brevity, we do not explain the above constraints since they are very similar to the ones in the previous section. Formulation (1)–(5) and (23)–(26) is referred to by MT2D because it uses triangles, a directed tour, and optimises the external area of the polygon. Observe that the system (23)–(25) becomes the system (19)–(21) when replacing $\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t$ with $1 - \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t$ for all $(i, j) \in A$. Still, we have observed empirically that MT1D and MT2D produce different LP bounds, and one does not dominate the other.

4.3. Selecting internal and external triangles

This section combines MT1D and MT2D using the three families of variables x_a , y_t and y'_t , earlier defined. We now look for a triangulation of N and also

Figure 3: subpolygons after drawing all possible edges of instance `uniform-0000010-1`.

for partitioning these triangles into T and T' . The new model, referred by `MT3D`, is (1)–(4) and (19)–(26). Note that this combined model does not need (5) to guarantee the non-crossing edges requirement.

4.4. Subpolygon-based Formulation

The previous formulations determine a polygon as the union of triangles. Alternatively, a polygon can be seen as the union of other smaller polygons (called *subpolygons*), not necessarily triangles. A natural candidate set of subpolygons to form a polygonisation of N is suggested by the graph $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$, drawing each arc $(i, j) \in A$ as a straight line between i and j . Some lines intersect, creating other points not in N , and the result is a mosaic of tiles, each one being a candidate subpolygon to be part of the optimal polygon. The result is a tessellation of the convex hull $\mathcal{CH}(N)$ (the subpolygons are the disjoint tiles). Figure 3 shows the 59 subpolygons on instance `uniform-0000010-1` with $|N|=10$. This section describes a new model based on selecting these subpolygons, and we start with notation.

Let W be the set of subpolygons generated with the above-described procedure on N . Without abuse of notation, each subpolygon $s \in W$ is the subset of arcs in A , each arc related to each edge of the subpolygon. As done in the previous section with the triangles, each subpolygon $s \in W$ is counterclockwise oriented, which determines the orientation of the arc related to each edge. Differently to the previous section, now the arc set s may not represent a circuit in $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$ since the vertices of the subpolygon s may not be in N .

Given $s, t \in W$, we say that s and t are *adjacent* if s and t share a line segment on the plane, meaning that there exist $(i, j) \in A''$ such that

$(i, j) \in s$ and $(j, i) \in t$. In such a case, we say that s is on the left of (i, j) and t is on the right of (i, j) . The set of all subpolygons on the left of an arc $(i, j) \in A$ is denoted by W_{ij} . Each edge $\{i, j\} \in E''$ is associated with a subset H_{ij} of pairs $\{s, t\}$ of adjacent subpolygons with $s \in W_{ij}$ and $t \in W_{ji}$. For example, the line segment $[2, 5]$ in Figure 3 separates three pairs of adjacent subpolygons. Finally, we denote by c_s the area of each subpolygon $s \in W$.

We use here again the variables x_a used in the previous models to determine the polygon and introduce the binary variable η_s for each $s \in W$, assuming value 1 if s is selected to cover the interior area of the polygon, and value 0 otherwise. Now, models for the MINAREA and MAXAREA are: (1)–(4) and

$$\eta_s = x_{ij} \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A' \text{ and } s \in W_{ij} \quad (27)$$

$$\eta_s - \eta_t = x_{ij} - x_{ji} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \text{ and } \{s, t\} \in H_{ij} : \quad (28)$$

$$s \in W_{ij}, t \in W_{ji}$$

$$x_{ij} \leq \eta_s \leq 1 - x_{ji} \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A'' \text{ and } s \in W_{ij}. \quad (29)$$

Equation (27) selects all subpolygons adjacent to a boundary line segment when the tour traverses this line segment. For each arc (i, j) separating the subpolygons s and t , with $s \in W_{ij}$ (i.e. left of (i, j)) and $t \in W_{ji}$ (i.e. right of (i, j)): Equations (28) force $\eta_s = \eta_t$ when $[i, j]$ is not traversed by the tour, and Constraints (29) imply $\eta_s = 1$ and $\eta_t = 0$ if $x_{ij} = 1$, and $\eta_s = 0$ and $\eta_t = 1$ if $x_{ji} = 1$. When the variables x_{ij} represent a Hamiltonian circuit, the linear system (27)–(29) has only one solution; thus, the integrability of the η_s variables is unnecessary. This linear system is related to the one proposed by Dantzig et al. (1985) for the triangulation of a set of points, aiming at covering each point in the convex hull with exactly one triangle.

Model (1)–(4) and (27)–(29) is referred by MSD since it uses subpolygon-based variables and the directed graph $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$. As in MT1D, Formulation MSD selects objects to cover the internal area of the polygon. One could expect another model, similar to MT2D, by selecting subpolygons to cover the external area. However, it is the same formulation.

It is worth observing that Model MSD is an aggregated version of MT3D.

Theorem 4. *The LP bound from MSD is not better than the one from MT3D.*

Proof. The result arises after duplicating (27)–(29) and replacing η_s with $\sum_{t \in V_s} y_t$ in one copy and with $1 - \sum_{t \in V_s} y'_t$ in the other copy, where V_s represents the triangles including the subpolygon s . \square

A potential advantage of MSD could be that $|W|$ could be expected to be smaller than $|V|$, thus a model with a smaller number of variables, and therefore an MILP could be faster in practice. Section 6 shows that this does not occur on our instances in part because Theorem 10 reduces V .

4.5. Edge-based Formulations

The previous new formulations replace the connectivity constraints (9) in the seminar triangle-based formulation with the Asymmetric TSP constraints (2)–(4). However, MINAREA and MAXAREA concern geometric objects in the Euclidean space. Thus, one could expect other formulations with Symmetric TSP constraints instead. This section shows how to adapt the formulations in the previous subsections to use edge-based variables x_e instead of arc-based variables x_a . The key element is to represent the polygon as a non-oriented tour in $\mathcal{G}(N, E)$ rather than a Hamiltonian circuit in $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$, and to compute an internal triangulation T of the polygon. To this end, we make use of the set V of counterclockwise-oriented triangles and the subsets V_{ij} and V_{ji} for each $\{i, j\} \in E$. Note that, while $V_{ij} \cup V_{ji}$ are all the triangles with the line segment $[i, j]$ being an edge, each triangle in $V_{ij} \cup V_{ji}$ has a third vertex k that is on one side of the line segment $[i, j]$. Precisely, all triangles in V_{ij} have the third vertex on the same side of $\{i, j\}$, and all triangles in V_{ji} have the third vertex on the other side. Note also that one of the two subsets is empty when $\{i, j\} \in E'$. The new model uses the already-introduced binary variable y_t for each $t \in V$, thus defining the selected triangulation by $T = \{t \in V : y_t = 1\}$.

Let us now introduce a new binary variable x'_e for each $e \in E$, assuming value 1 when e is in the tour and 0 otherwise. We write indistinctly x'_e or x'_{ij} or x'_{ji} when $e = \{i, j\}$. All the formulations in this section use the x'_e variables to determine the edges of the polygon. A Symmetric TSP solution is determined by (for example) the following integer linear system:

$$\sum_{e \in \delta(i)} x'_e = 2 \quad \text{for all } i \in N \quad (30)$$

$$\sum_{e \in E(S)} x'_e \leq |S| - 1 \quad \text{for all } S \subset N \quad (31)$$

$$x'_e \in \{0, 1\} \quad \text{for all } e \in E. \quad (32)$$

The non-crossing edges requirement can be guaranteed with

$$x'_{ij} + x'_{kl} \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } \{[i, j], [k, l]\} \in I_2. \quad (33)$$

Now, Model MT1D suggests formulating MINAREA and MAXAREA by the objective function (7) subject to (30)–(33) and

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t + \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y_t = x'_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E' \quad (34)$$

$$-x'_{ij} \leq \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t - \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y_t \leq x'_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \quad (35)$$

$$x'_{ij} \leq \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t + \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y_t \leq 2 - x'_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \quad (36)$$

$$y_t \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in V. \quad (37)$$

Equations (34) force selecting one adjacent triangle to each edge on the boundary of the convex hull of N , and no one otherwise. These equations ensure that the selected triangles are in the internal region of the polygon. Inequalities (35) force that either zero or two triangles are selected if the edge is not in the tour. Inequalities (36) force one adjacent triangle to be selected if the edge is in the tour, and at most two adjacent triangles may be selected otherwise.

A proof similar to that of Theorem 2 produces the following result.

Theorem 5. *When variables x'_e represent a simple polygonization of N , all the extreme solutions of (34)–(37) are integers.*

The new formulation (7) and (30)–(37) is referred to by MT1U. In contrast to previous models, the objective function (1) is not an option since variables x_a are not present.

Model MT2D suggests selecting an external triangulation T' using y'_t binary variables, so $T' = \{t \in V : y'_t = 1\}$. The new formulations for MINAREA and MAXAREA are defined by the objective function

$$\text{min/max} \quad c(\mathcal{CH}(N)) - \sum_{t \in V} c_t y'_t$$

subject to (30)–(33) and

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t + \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y'_t = 1 - x'_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E' \quad (38)$$

$$-x'_{ij} \leq \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t - \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y'_t \leq x'_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \quad (39)$$

$$x'_{ij} \leq \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t + \sum_{t \in V_{ji}} y'_t \leq 2 - x'_{ij} \quad \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \quad (40)$$

$$y'_t \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } t \in V. \quad (41)$$

Theorem 6. *When variables x'_e represent a simple polygonization of N , all the extreme solutions of (38)–(41) are integers.*

The new formulation is referred to by MT2U. As already observed on models MT1D and MT2D, the system (38)–(40) becomes the system (34)–(36) by replacing $\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t$ with $1 - \sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t$ for all $(i, j) \in A$.

Model MT3D suggests formulating MINAREA and MAXAREA with the constraints (30)–(32) and (34)–(41). This model does not need (33) to force the non-crossing edges requirement. As for the objective function, we can use the one in MT1D or MT2D, or even a convex combination like:

$$\min/\max \quad \frac{1}{2}c(\mathcal{CH}(N)) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t \in V} c_t(y_t - y'_t).$$

The formulation with this objective function is referred to by MT3U.

Using the linear equation $x'_{ij} = x_{ij} + x_{ji}$ for each $\{i, j\} \in E$ one gets:

Lemma 7. *Each solution of (19)–(26) is also a solution of (34)–(41).*

Theorem 8. *The LP bound from MT3U is not better than the one from MT3D.*

Given a Hamiltonian circuit with non-crossing arcs described by the oriented arc-based variables x_a for $a \in A$, one can check the existence of the internal and external triangulations with the system (34)–(41) instead of the system (19)–(26) (since both systems define the same integer polytope). Empirically, we have observed that MILP solvers manage the system (34)–(41) with more difficulties because it has fewer equations and more inequalities than the system (19)–(26). In addition, when the variables x_a determine a fractional TSP solution, we also observed that the polytope defined by (34)–(41) may include other non-integer extreme points than the ones in (19)–(26). For that reason, there is no gain in using (34)–(41) with oriented variables x_a . Instead, the smaller number of non-oriented variables x'_e could perhaps compensate for the weak LP bound of MT3U. Unfortunately, Section 6 shows that this is not the case in our benchmark instances.

Given a Hamiltonian tour with non-crossing edges described by the non-oriented variables x'_e , one could also think of a counterclockwise oriented Hamiltonian circuit to later check the existence of a triangulation with the system (19)–(26). However, in this case, we do not have a linear system defining x_{ij} and x_{ji} from x'_{ij} .

Finally, Model MSD suggests another edge-based formulation. Let W and H defined as in Section 4.4. Now, the MINAREA and MAXAREA can be modelled by the objective function

$$\min/\max \sum_{s \in W} c_s \eta_s$$

subject to (30)–(32) and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_s &= x'_{ij} && \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E' \text{ and } s \in W_{ij} \cup W_{ji} \\ -x'_{ij} &\leq \eta_s - \eta_t \leq x'_{ij} && \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \text{ and } \{s, t\} \in H_{ij} \\ x'_{ij} &\leq \eta_s + \eta_t \leq 2 - x'_{ij} && \text{for all } \{i, j\} \in E'' \text{ and } \{s, t\} \in H_{ij}. \end{aligned}$$

The new formulation is referred to by MSU.

Theorem 9. *The LP bound from MSU is not better than the one from MSD.*

4.6. Reformulation of Model (1)–(6)

We close this section with a reformulation of Model (1)–(6) to have it in the same framework as the other models and perform a fair computational comparison in Section 6. Model MT1D includes y_t variables to triangulate inside the circuit. Model MT2D includes y'_t variables to triangulate outside the circuit. Model MT3D includes both y_t and y'_t . Now Model (1)–(6) by Fekete et al. (2022) can be seen as the remaining case, i.e., it is an arc-based model without y_t and y'_t . For that reason, we refer to it as Model MOD.

Since there is no triangulation in Model MOD, the area of the polygon is forced to be computed with the objective function (1). This objective function needs additional constraints on the x_a variables to avoid a counterclockwise-oriented circuit (and make the model valid for MINAREA). An alternative to the slab constraints (6) when using the TSP representation (2)–(4) is to exploit the precedence relations between the points on the convex-hull boundary N' . See e.g. Balas et al. (1995) for valid linear inequalities to force a point i to be before a point j in a circuit starting and ending at point r , with $i, j, r \in N'$. Section 5.2 shows a simpler procedure when the TSP constraints are modelled with flow variables.

5. Implementation details

This section describes the main ingredients of a method to solve the formulations in this paper with a general-purpose MILP solver.

5.1. Variable fixing

The triangle-based models suffer the inconvenience of a (simple) polygon admitting many triangulations. The number of triangulations of a convex polygon with n vertices is the so-called $(n-2)$ -Catalan number (see e.g. Lora et al. (2010)), which is large. The number of triangulations is smaller for non-convex polygons, but it may still be very large, meaning that triangle-based models may include many variables y_t and y'_t (and many alternative solutions representing the same polygon). The following result helps to eliminate some variables. Let $A''_I = \{(i, j) \in A : (i, j) \in A'' : i, j \in N'\}$ and $E''_I = \{\{i, j\} : (i, j) \in A''_I\}$. Fekete et al. (2022) observe that a polygonisation of N cannot have an edge on an arc $(i, j) \in A''_I$ because there are other points on both sides of the line segment determined by i and j . Thus, they fix $x_a = 0$ when $a \in A''_I$. The following result extends the fixing also to the y_t and y'_t variables.

Theorem 10. *A non-convex polygon on the plane admits a triangulation where triangles do not include edges in E''_I .*

Proof. For each $\{i, j\} \in E''_I$, a triangulation with a triangle in V_{ij} has another triangle in V_{ji} . Let k, l be the other vertices of these triangles. If $k \notin N'$ or $l \notin N'$, replace the two triangles with one in V_{kl} and another in V_{lk} . Otherwise, select the triangle from the triangulation adjacent to one of the previous triangles. The new triangle brings in another vertex q . The procedure repeats until $q \notin N'$, and then one must replace the considered triangles with ones from V_q . The replacement is possible because all the considered vertices determine a convex subpolygon. \square

As a consequence, the LP relaxations of the models are stronger with:

- $x_a = 0$ for all $a \in A''_I$,
- $x'_e = 0$ for all $e \in E''_I$,
- $y_t = y'_t = 0$ for all $t \in V_a$ and $a \in A''_I$,
- $\eta_s = 1$ for all $s \in W_a$ and $a \in A''_I$.

5.2. TSP representations

The new models for MINAREA and MAXAREA force the connectivity constraints between selected objects using TSP variables and constraints. TSP has been deeply investigated, and there are several alternative MILP formulations. We have used (2)–(4) for the oriented variant and (30)–(32)

for the non-oriented variant. Modern TSP solvers deal with large instances managing (3) and (31) through branch-and-cut algorithms. However, since MINAREA and MAXAREA seem to be more complex problems (30 points is challenging), it makes sense to replace these exponential-size formulations with compact ones. The price to pay for having a polynomial number of constraints is to add a polynomial number of continuous variables. This section shows an alternative. Let r be the arbitrary point taken from N' .

The so-called “multi-commodity flow formulation” for the TSP uses a variable f_a^k for each $k \in V \setminus \{r\}$ and each $a \in A$. It takes a positive value if a path along the tour from r to k goes through arc a . Then, an oriented tour in $\mathcal{G}(N, A)$ can be modelled with (2), (4) and

$$\sum_{a \in \delta^-(i)} f_a^k - \sum_{a \in \delta^+(i)} f_a^k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = k \\ -1 & \text{if } i = r \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{for all } k \in N \setminus \{r\} \quad (42)$$

$$0 \leq f_a^k \leq x_a \quad \text{for all } k \in N \setminus \{r\} \text{ and } a \in A$$

provides LP bounds equal to the TSP formulation using (3). In addition, the flow variables also allow modelling the counterclockwise orientation with

$$\sum_{a \in \delta^+(i)} f_a^j = 1 \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A' : i, j \in N' \setminus \{r\}$$

instead of the Slab Constraints (6).

Similarly, a non-oriented tour can be modelled with (30), (32), (42) and

$$f_{ij}^k \geq 0, f_{ji}^k \geq 0, f_{ij}^k + f_{ji}^k = x'_{ij}/2 \quad \text{for all } k \in N \setminus \{r\} \text{ and } \{i, j\} \in E$$

instead of the so-called Subtour Elimination Constraints (31).

5.3. Non-crossing edges requirement

Covering the internal and external areas of a polygon by triangles or sub-polygons guarantees the non-crossing edges requirements, i.e. the polygon generated from models MT3D, MT3U and MSD is simple. Hence, Inequalities (5) and (33) are unnecessary to have valid formulations. Still, adding them may strengthen the LP relaxation, especially when they are lifted as we now describe.

Given $\{[i, j], [k, l]\} \in I_2$, Inequality (5) is dominated by

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y_t + x_{ji} + \sum_{t \in V_{kl}} y_t + x_{lk} \leq 1$$

and

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} y'_t + x_{ij} + \sum_{t \in V_{kl}} y'_t + x_{kl} \leq 1.$$

Based on our computational experiments, they strengthen the LP relaxation of MT1D and MT2D, respectively. Similarly, Inequality (33) suggests

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} (y_t + y'_t) + \sum_{t \in V_{kl}} (y_t + y'_t) \leq 1,$$

which may strengthen the LP relaxation of MT3U.

It is known in the MILP literature that the above inequalities create incompatibilities between variables, and the LP relaxations can then be strengthened with further linear inequalities. In this direction, Fekete et al. (2022) refer to *maximal clique inequalities* and *halfspace constraints*, which are heuristically generated within a branch-and-cut framework. Modern MILP solvers already implement internal functions to generate similar inequalities when incompatibilities are detected in the given formulation. Thus, we do not extend this article in this direction.

5.4. Other valid linear constraints

Equalities (11), $\sum_{t \in T} y'_t = |N| - |N'|$ and $\sum_{t \in T} c_t (y_t + y'_t) = c(\mathcal{CH}(N))$, and the inequalities

$$\sum_{t \in V_{ij}} (y_t + y'_t) \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } (i, j) \in A$$

strengthen LP relaxations, according to our computational experiments.

5.5. Alternative objective-function coefficients

When the Cartesian coordinates of i and j are (α_i, β_i) and (α_j, β_j) , respectively, the coefficient c_{ij} in the objective function (1) may be fixed to $(\alpha_i \beta_j - \alpha_j \beta_i) / 2$. Other alternative definitions of c_{ij} to compute the polygon's area are possible, like $(\alpha_i + \alpha_j)(\beta_j - \beta_i) / 2$ or $(\beta_i + \beta_j)(\alpha_i - \alpha_j) / 2$. In all cases, $c_{ij} = -c_{ji}$, which makes the coefficient matrix highly asymmetric.

As observed in Section 3, when using a formulation with *only* the arc-based variables x_a , additional constraints are necessary to force the counterclockwise orientation of the circuit. These constraints are unnecessary for the new arc-based models in Section 4 because the counterclockwise orientation is in each triangle or subpolygon, and then the linear systems extend this orientation to the circuit. This simple observation implies that, for

example, Models MT1D and MT3D can be reformulated using the objective function (7) instead of (1). Computational experiments showed better performance when using (7). This choice does not apply to Model MOD because variables y_t and y'_t are absent, hence (1) is mandatory. There is no choice on the edge-based models either because variables x_a are absent.

All formulations compute the area of a polygon by adding the areas of pieces (triangles or subpolygons). The literature on Computational Geometry has different alternatives to compute these areas. We now show one of these procedures, known as *Pick's Theorem* (see e.g. Mark Berg and Schwarzkopf (1997)), which we found particularly interesting for the subpolygon-based models. The procedure assumes that each vertex in N is a grid point (i.e. a point with integer coordinates) on the Cartesian plane, and it determines the area of a polygonisation P of N by counting the grid points in the interior of P and on the boundary of P , as follows:

Theorem 11. *Let P be a polygon whose vertices have integer coordinates on the Cartesian plane. Then the area of P is the sum of the number of grid points in the interior of P , plus half the number of grid points on the boundary of P , minus one.*

The above result gives an alternative evaluation of the area c_t of a triangle $t \in T$ and c_s of a subpolygon $s \in W$. Recall that we assume that the coordinates of N are integers. Then, the area of a triangle is already a half-integer. However, the vertices of a subpolygon may likely have non-integer coordinates and, therefore, the area may be a fractional number. Instead, with the above result, this number is replaced by a half-integer in the objective function. The replacement reduces numerical issues and benefits modern solvers. Computational experiments showed better performance of MSD and MSU when using this approach.

5.6. Integrality constraints

Theorem 2 guarantees that the variables y_t assume integer values when the variables x_a are forced to be binary. Conversely, the variables x_a assume integer values when y_t is required to be a binary variable. Computational experiments showed us that the performance is better in the former setting.

5.7. Initial heuristic

An initial feasible solution may help an MILP solver on a model. We propose a simple constructive procedure starting from the convex hull $\mathcal{CH}(N)$, improved with a 2-edge-exchange search. The constructive heuristic starts

from the counterclockwise tour through N' . Then, it inserts the point $k \in N \setminus N'$ between consecutive points i and j of the current tour such that the area of the triangle $\{i, j, k\}$ is maximum when solving MINAREA and minimum when solving MAXAREA and the line segments $[i, k]$ and $[j, k]$ do not cross the tour. The procedure continues until all points are in the tour. The 2-edge-exchange search checks whether each point should be better placed between two other consecutive points in the current tour.

6. Computational results

We have implemented a computer code in C++ to use CPLEX 22.11 as the MILP solver on the formulations in this paper. The code was run on a personal computer DELL-T5810 with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-1630 v3 @ 3.70 GHz, 32 GB of RAM, and Microsoft Windows 10.

As in Ramos et al. (2022b), we run the computer code on the dataset collection of instances with $|N| \in \{10, 15, 20\}$ available on a public website² to compare the nine formulations. Each line of Table 1 shows the average results over 10 instances. *IPtime* refers to the computational time measured in seconds to achieve optimality, and *LPgap* refers to the percentage gap between the LP bound and the value of an optimal MILP solution. More precisely, for each model, let *LPvalue* be the optimal value of the LP relaxation and *IPvalue* be the objective value of an optimal MILP solution; *LPgap* is $100(IPvalue - LPvalue)/IPvalue$ for the MINAREA, and $100(LPvalue - IPvalue)/(c(\mathcal{CH}(N)) - IPvalue)$ for the MAXAREA. By doing so, 100% means that the LP bound was the weakest (0 for the MINAREA and the convex hull area of N for the MAXAREA). Regarding computational time to get an optimal MILP solution, MT1D seems comparable to MT3D on MINAREA instances, and MT2D seems comparable to MT3D on MAXAREA instances. The edge-based models produced worse LP bounds (as expected) and required more time to finish than the arc-based models. The subpolygon-based models also showed poor performance compared to the triangle-based models and, indeed, some of these executions stopped by the time limit (one hour) without an optimal MILP solution.

To further explore the performance of MT3D on larger instances, we considered the benchmark collection of instances in Fekete et al. (2022), publicly available on a website¹. This collection consists of 54 instances with $10 \leq |N| \leq 50$, and each instance is the input for MINAREA and MAXAREA.

²www.ic.unicamp.br/~cid/Problem-instances/Area-Optimal-Simple-Poly

N	MOD		MT1D		MT2D		MT3D		MSD		MT1U		MT2U		MT3U		MSU	
	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>	<i>IPtime</i>	<i>LPgap</i>
MINAREA																		
10	0.2	94.1	0.0	8.0	0.0	31.7	0.0	5.7	0.2	47.2	0.0	8.0	0.0	31.7	0.0	7.5	0.2	54.8
15	9.6	100.0	0.4	29.8	0.7	83.8	0.5	20.0	15.9	78.8	0.6	29.9	1.4	83.8	1.4	45.8	75.3	82.1
20	1375.7	100.0	7.5	44.9	31.7	96.8	6.0	26.4	1326.0 ¹	85.6	22.6	45.0	79.7	96.8	61.3	70.1	3600.0 ¹⁰	91.7
MAXAREA																		
10	0.0	100.0	0.0	70.9	0.0	3.4	0.0	2.6	0.0	28.8	0.0	70.9	0.0	3.4	0.0	6.7	0.0	46.7
15	1.3	100.0	0.7	100.0	0.1	12.8	0.1	11.0	1.3	61.9	1.8	100.0	0.1	11.5	0.8	72.3	11.1	67.6
20	185.8	100.0	46.0	100.0	1.2	32.3	1.6	24.7	92.9	79.2	189.4	100.0	2.4	32.5	43.7	88.5	1635.7 ²	82.9

Table 1: Average computational times and gaps using the models. The super-index indicates the number of instances stopped by the time limit without MILP optimality.

Table 2 shows the number of variables and constraints in the MT3D model for each instance, the features *LPvalue*, *LPgap*, *IPvalue* and *IPtime* previously defined, and also the number *IPnodes* of explored branch-and-bound nodes. Fekete et al. (2022) used a computer similar to our computer and with a time limit of 43,800 seconds. We set a time limit of 60,000 seconds on our computer. Unfortunately, there are potential errors in their tables; some are formatting typos, but others are wrong numbers (e.g., the optimal MINAREA value of `uniform-0000050-2` cannot be 1094266 because it admits a polygonisation with internal area equal to 1088120). Ignoring these potential errors, Fekete et al. (2022) claim to have found optimal solutions to 28 MAXAREA instances and 28 MINAREA instances. As shown in Table 2, using MT3D, our code finds optimal solutions to all instances in their benchmark collection except three MINAREA instances with 50 points.

7. Conclusions

This paper presents ten mathematical MILP formulations for finding simple polygonisations of a given set of points on the Cartesian plane with minimum and maximum area. Two are known formulations, and eight are new models. The first four new models represent the polygon as an Asymmetric TSP solution, while the other four represent the polygon as a Symmetric TSP solution. In each family, three models select triangles (one to cover the internal area, another to cover the external area, and the third to cover both), and a fourth model selects subpolygons. The LP relaxations of the oriented models give better bounds. The winner approach is an oriented TSP model with triangle-based variables. According to Ramos et al. (2022b), all instances in a benchmark collection with up to 15 points were optimally solved, some with 20, a few with 25, and none with 30 points. Now, with the winner model MT3D, all these instances are solved to optimality in a few seconds of computational time on a personal computer. In addition,

MT3D allowed finding optimal solutions to all the instances in Fekete et al. (2022) except three MINAREA instances with 50 points.

This paper also opens challenging research lines. The first need is to investigate a theoretical proof that the LP bounds from models MOD, MT1D and MT2D are never better than the ones from model MT3D. Our computational results support this claim. Our experiments also suggest finding new families of inequalities to reduce the LP bounds, which are over 45% far from the optimal MILP objective value for the three unsolved instances in the benchmark collection. Since model MT3D is a TSP formulation with additional continuous variables, applying a Benders' Decomposition of MT3D and replacing the continuous variables with Benders' cuts may solve larger instances. Using the objective function (1), only feasibility Benders' cuts are needed. The combinatorial structure under these cuts deserves to be investigated and, potentially, used to strengthen these inequalities and derive an efficient branch-and-cut approach. Another research question is finding inequalities on the triangle-based variables y_t to model the pioneer connectivity constraints (9) without needing TSP variables. While our investigations reveal better LP relaxations when representing a polygon by an oriented tour, there may exist other linear inequalities to strengthen the LP relaxations when representing a polygon by a non-oriented tour. Even more challenging is extending the new models to deal with points in a d -dimensional space where polygons turn to polytopes, and area turns to volume.

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instance		MT3D size		MINAREA					MAXAREA					
name	N	c(CH(N))	columns	rows	LPvalue	LPgap	IPvalue	IPtime	IPnodes	LPvalue	LPgap	IPvalue	IPtime	IPnodes
euro-night-0000010	10	31906376	276	435	9954272.00	0.00	9954272	0.02	1	28509725.00	0.32	28498980	0.04	1
euro-night-0000015	15	41855016	798	1038	5097734.33	28.28	7107334	0.45	43	38318784.86	9.19	37961104	0.21	1
euro-night-0000020	20	47757658	1560	1882	4545671.08	32.19	6703352	1.72	340	44732464.45	29.72	43453166	1.09	174
euro-night-0000025	25	55948734	2664	2988	4244529.65	31.92	6235066	14.34	1678	52199607.70	27.43	50782240	10.85	1593
euro-night-0000030	30	57242274	3984	4332	4389291.03	38.96	7190308	102.21	5542	54316476.23	33.68	52830622	25.71	1766
euro-night-0000035	35	49249648	5634	5929	3576331.89	34.62	5470084	285.23	11316	46653149.94	24.31	45819094	51.85	3301
euro-night-0000040	40	50769218	7820	7779	2570002.47	41.90	4423466	1186.16	22869	49050869.26	39.90	47910104	422.56	18859
euro-night-0000045	45	51682796	9724	9873	3499591.26	38.00	5644412	9506.71	192212	49494735.73	36.91	48214668	1253.65	19828
euro-night-0000050	50	65414966	12062	12223	3670481.44	48.68	7152842	unsolved	556627	62671280.29	45.30	60399328	43056.36	390990
london-0000010	10	107220528	282	438	19207298.00	0.00	19207298	0.02	1	95364394.00	0.00	95364394	0.02	1
london-0000015	15	135654760	784	1035	15473568.00	13.11	17809096	0.28	1	128462757.72	9.25	127729316	0.14	1
london-0000020	20	223165922	1582	1885	31344928.78	23.51	40978058	1.82	211	205027076.00	19.92	200514948	0.89	99
london-0000025	25	247641924	2612	2982	24559717.63	23.10	31936238	6.22	597	234365914.00	17.53	231544442	3.14	301
london-0000030	30	165716840	4038	4338	8771892.92	43.53	15533240	124.65	7926	156269273.89	32.58	151703726	38.42	2757
london-0000035	35	232900980	5704	5932	13497421.70	46.68	25312358	1575.10	35898	220776391.26	31.85	215109002	70.98	4015
london-0000040	40	237643814	7736	7782	19873878.49	44.65	35905290	9596.11	286651	218719220.62	32.34	209674650	1902.95	35388
london-0000045	45	295993302	9530	9879	17755861.54	46.72	33322976	58484.83	480915	279030788.76	31.57	271205760	3068.98	39021
london-0000050	50	251055646	11994	12226	16030247.70	48.99	31422758	unsolved	431110	239415925.66	41.70	231089684	54347.69	475898
stars-0000010	10	138819316472	292	438	40264246222.00	0.00	40264246222	0.03	1	127476507282.00	0.00	127476507282	0.02	1
stars-0000015	15	152074927004	778	1032	27934034422.00	6.19	29776831822	0.23	1	144138236108.00	17.36	142470465062	0.13	1
stars-0000020	20	228954543338	1460	1876	32358471880.88	21.16	41041275182	2.27	429	218494081400.12	14.34	216742984910	0.52	1
stars-0000025	25	254745005286	2672	2979	22144812334.25	38.30	35893175226	24.91	1995	240709012623.83	19.50	237309787430	2.39	118
stars-0000030	30	200579422660	3912	4326	21309374701.58	24.75	28318464852	58.67	1914	189582078832.38	29.15	185057287956	26.56	1295
stars-0000035	35	243392117560	5612	5929	21313548024.98	35.77	33183160522	806.44	19733	230146613954.33	36.81	222429730998	137.84	3868
stars-0000040	40	211974652624	7416	7776	21523820407.34	37.25	34302635012	6617.39	97609	198391830242.76	37.69	190177150422	866.12	16877
stars-0000045	45	266232485330	9694	9876	18857129451.14	40.18	31524828442	31579.58	191932	253180783837.03	38.39	245048373286	18424.33	117751
stars-0000050	50	264902562116	12610	12226	14395127150.60	45.93	26625487604	unsolved	200606	254874743575.03	41.67	247712484090	25617.44	139307
uniform-0000010-1	10	167380	274	435	58872.00	0.00	58872	0.02	1	148583.33	2.96	148010	0.03	1
uniform-0000010-2	10	156160	250	432	51568.00	0.00	51568	0.03	1	151540.00	0.00	151540	0.02	1
uniform-0000015-1	15	423856	762	1032	74212.00	27.75	102716	0.66	184	395909.60	13.70	391474	0.13	1
uniform-0000015-2	15	414526	726	1029	113436.00	0.00	113436	0.06	1	377505.00	7.47	374516	0.09	1
uniform-0000020-1	20	881586	1588	1882	151226.78	19.66	188242	1.22	97	772877.75	9.12	761968	1.05	1
uniform-0000020-2	20	873076	1628	1882	102307.87	21.59	130478	1.11	45	809150.59	6.47	804730	0.45	1
uniform-0000025-1	25	1581748	2700	2982	223096.77	30.28	319974	18.54	2635	1373305.12	20.34	1320082	7.21	1160
uniform-0000025-2	25	1552440	2632	2976	245179.34	30.24	351446	14.27	1862	1419492.91	23.09	1379588	2.67	347
uniform-0000030-1	30	2125854	3838	4320	261057.35	30.11	373510	59.23	3055	2018191.03	36.59	1956068	44.17	3709
uniform-0000030-2	30	2493678	3958	4323	265731.91	37.77	427002	97.57	6900	2365759.89	30.45	2309760	8.90	701
uniform-0000035-1	35	3498494	5556	5923	295782.95	40.82	499776	488.58	26587	3319348.85	32.10	3234656	43.48	2155
uniform-0000035-2	35	3530464	6060	5929	305257.91	29.15	430856	383.62	18040	3318030.90	22.77	3255396	34.20	1640
uniform-0000040-1	40	4830682	7650	7767	478875.01	38.44	777956	2164.17	75370	4606899.21	43.96	4431360	395.91	17263
uniform-0000040-2	40	4549512	7798	7776	379484.97	39.39	626084	1593.97	43569	4293865.79	32.60	4170194	217.75	6946
uniform-0000045-1	45	5231150	9780	9870	504884.50	37.96	813802	19951.42	503294	4931456.07	36.48	4759374	1042.39	25710
uniform-0000045-2	45	5682168	9906	9879	392328.46	47.10	741648	12792.69	291283	5357371.02	38.02	5158094	2740.24	73725
uniform-0000050-1	50	6899710	12606	12229	398707.55	36.21	625044	11740.59	144933	6591862.76	39.94	6387130	27320.31	557402
uniform-0000050-2	50	7848422	12508	12223	649537.47	40.31	1088120	38044.95	603244	7435176.85	40.73	7151224	10236.48	158048
us-night-0000010	10	14539898	300	438	3113682.00	14.71	3650560	0.06	1	13059816.00	0.00	13059816	0.02	1
us-night-0000015	15	69904148	786	1035	14977509.85	10.00	16642190	0.19	1	62208264.50	19.90	60295830	0.49	1
us-night-0000020	20	58020532	1612	1885	5073813.31	23.30	6615280	1.91	341	55379694.00	23.65	54561746	1.03	108
us-night-0000025	25	65652246	2674	2979	6457760.61	29.22	9123288	16.25	2241	61859409.05	25.14	60585868	6.48	1125
us-night-0000030	30	71208982	3962	4332	3652991.95	36.47	5750296	48.45	2162	68257080.22	40.86	66217320	110.67	10813
us-night-0000035	35	83934560	5606	5932	5119010.90	49.43	10123092	1481.59	62140	79392179.85	33.19	77135624	266.26	15698
us-night-0000040	40	72938128	7776	7779	3176652.68	39.69	5267414	2055.90	47083	70517435.27	39.44	68940956	1031.21	40588
us-night-0000045	45	80203854	10332	9879	2157125.48	40.00	3595152	2242.72	27199	78587730.33	28.58	77941112	273.75	3802
us-night-0000050	50	83181940	13184	12223	3244749.55	35.80	5054470	10152.40	38570	81231824.94	39.60	79952918	3334.01	38570

Table 2: Results using MT3D model to solve the benchmark instances in Fekete et al. (2022).